

Current Sharing Dynamics During IGBT ZVS Turn-On in a Hybrid Si IGBT/SiC MOSFET Switch

Marco Andrade^{1,2}, Bernardo Cougo¹, Lenin M F Morais²

¹IRT Saint Exupery - Toulouse, France

²Graduate Program in Electrical Engineering, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais - Belo Horizonte, Brazil

E-Mail: marco.andrade@irt-saintexupery.com, bernardo.cogo@irt-saintexupery.com, lenin@cpdee.ufmg.br URL:

www.irt-saintexupery.com¹ / www.ppgee.ufmg.br²

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101007513. The JU receives support from the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation program and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union.

Index Terms—SiC MOSFET, IGBT, Power semiconductor device, Paralleling, Parasitic Inductance.

Abstract—This article describes the switching dynamic of current in a 1200V Si IGBT/SiC MOSFET hybrid switch for Aircraft Applications, and its associated losses. A method to measure the dynamic behavior of this hybrid switch and precisely determine losses during the switching process is presented and experimentally verified.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parallel connection of transistors is a traditional strategy to support higher currents in power converters. Usually the same transistors are connected in parallel. These power converters are traditionally composed by silicon (Si) MOSFET for low voltage applications, and Si IGBTs for high voltage applications. This scenario changes with the introduction of wide bandgap (WBG) semiconductors, such as silicon carbide (SiC) MOSFET and gallium nitride (GaN) HEMT. Nowadays different transistor technologies are competing in the same blocking voltage levels.

In this scenario, the parallel connection of transistors can be made with different transistor technologies to take advantage of the best characteristics of each technology. In the 1200V blocking voltage devices, the available technologies are Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET. The Si/SiC hybrid switch (HyS) is the combination of these two technologies to take advantage of the best characteristics of the SiC MOSFET (fast commutation, low switching

losses and low conduction losses at small currents), and those of the IGBT (low voltage drop at high currents and lower cost than SiC) [1]–[3]. The typical circuit of this HyS is shown in Figure 1, where we specifically represent the parasitic inductance between the components, a key element in the dynamics studied in this paper.

Fig. 1. A hybrid switch composed of SiC MOSFET, Si IGBT, and diode. Parasitic inductance L between HyS is represented since it is a key factor in the dynamics studied in this paper.

Figure 2 shows some switching patterns that allow us to take full advantage of the HyS, optimizing total switching and conduction losses. Pattern 1 brings simplicity to gate driver and control logic by using a single signal to both switches. Patterns 2 and 3 can be created with circuits presented in [4], [5] and are used to optimize switching losses in the hybrid switch by switching the IGBT at zero voltage. Studies in [6], [7] focus on optimizing patterns 2 and 3 considering the trade-off between reduction in Si IGBT switching losses, and extra conduction losses to optimize performance. Pattern 4 is used to reduce SiC MOSFET usage reducing the required die size or to achieve better thermal balance between IGBT and SiC MOSFET [8], [9].

Both [6], [7] discuss the delay patterns 2 and 3 and the switching energy considering not only turn on

Fig. 2. Switching patterns that can be used in a Si/SiC Hybrid Switch, adapted from [5].

and turn-off energies, but also the energy lost due to conduction during delay. They identify the presence of extra conduction losses during the time when the SiC is conducting alone, but they calculate these losses using static parameters of the devices. They also consider that the current divides instantaneously between SiC and IGBT after its turn-on delay to calculate this extra conduction loss. This is not the case due to the parasitic inductance between the parallel SiC and IGBT and this dynamic is shown in the present work. This article then add to these past works a more precise view in the IGBT ZVS turn on dynamic in the HyS. It also presents a methodology to measure extra conduction losses that exist as a consequence of the delay. The methodology has the possibility to isolate the losses due to the ZVS turn on dynamic, which allow us to measure its relevance to total extra conduction losses.

The studied hybrid switch is composed of a $75\text{ m}\Omega/23\text{ A}$ SiC MOSFET, a 40 A Si IGBT and a 40 A SiC Schottky Diode. All with 1200 V blocking voltage and in a TO-247 package. The target application is a $540\text{ V}-600\text{ V}/30\text{ kW}$ converter for aeronautic application. The idea is to find a more cost-effective alternative to full SiC converters for the same application as shown in [10].

Equations for the current dynamic in a delayed Si IGBT turn-on in a HyS are presented in Section II, where the similar behavior between SiC MOSFET turn-on after dead time with reverse current is discussed. In Section III, experimental results are obtained to validate the model. Following, in Section IV, conduction loss components in the hybrid switch are identified and the mean conduction power loss relation to switching

frequency is presented. In Section V, a methodology to measure extra conduction losses in a hybrid switch is discussed, and results are compared to equations found in IV to identify extra switching losses. Finally, Section VI concludes this work.

II. HYBRID SWITCH LARGE SIGNAL MODEL

To analyze switching dynamics of a HyS, the conduction loss model discussed in [7] is expanded by including parasitic inductance between individual components of a HyS. This represents a large signals models of the HyS, and the corresponding circuit is shown in Figure 3. The circuit includes the MOSFET on-state resistance R_{DSON} , the MOSFET body diode represented as a forward voltage drop V_{BD} and series resistance R_{BD} . The Si IGBT is also represented by its forward voltage V_I and series resistance R_I . Finally, the discrete diode uses the same model with forward voltage drop V_D and series resistance R_D . Ideal diodes are represented to indicate the direction that each component can contribute to conduction. To represent if the IGBT and MOSFET are in ON or OFF state, ideal switches are represented: G_M for the MOSFET channel and G_I for the IGBT. To simplify the problem, the parasitic inductance L is considered to be the same for all devices. The described dynamic occurs when the device is under low voltage, and voltage swing is small, therefore the output parasitic capacitance is not considered.

Fig. 3. Large signal model of the HyS in conduction. The MOSFET model is represented in red, the IGBT model is represented in blue and an optional discrete diode model is in green.

Circuit in Figure 3 is used to analyze two situations: **Situation 1** - A HyS is being operated with pattern 3 from Figure 2, and positive I_{HyS} . At $t = T_1$, G_M is closed and the MOSFET conducts all I_{HyS} . After t_{don} , G_I is closed. If the voltage drop in the MOSFET R_{DSON}

is smaller than IGBT forward voltage V_I , the current will continue to flow only through the MOSFET. Otherwise, part of the current will flow through the IGBT. Current transfer will not be instantaneous. Transfer speed will depend on parasitic inductance and follow a RL dynamic, and this is the main phenomenon studied in this work. In this case, one can model the system by applying Kirchhoff laws arriving at the differential system formed by (1) and (2) with initial conditions (3). For simplicity $t' = t - T_1 - t_{don}$.

$$I_{HyS} = I_M(t') + I_I(t') \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{DSON} \cdot I_M(t') + L \frac{dI_M(t')}{dt} &= \\ &= V_I + R_I \cdot I_I(t') + L \frac{dI_I(t')}{dt} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$I_M(t' = 0) = I_{HyS} \quad (3)$$

Where the voltage, current, inductance and resistance values are shown in Figure 3. Solving the system we have equations (4) and (5) for the MOSFET and IGBT currents respectively, with the time constant τ_1 , defined in (6). In steady state, these equations present the same result as shown in [7].

$$\begin{aligned} I_M(t') &= \frac{I_{HyS} \cdot R_I + V_I}{R_{DSON} + R_I} + \\ &+ \frac{(I_{HyS} \cdot R_{DSON} - V_I)e^{-\frac{t'}{\tau_1}}}{R_{DSON} + R_I} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_I(t') &= \frac{I_{HyS} \cdot R_{DSON} - V_I}{R_{DSON} + R_I} + \\ &+ \frac{(-I_{HyS} \cdot R_{DSON} + V_I)e^{-\frac{t'}{\tau_1}}}{R_{DSON} + R_I} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\tau_1 = \frac{2 \cdot L}{R_{DSON} + R_I} \quad (6)$$

After the IGBT turn-off at $t = T_2 - T_{doff}$ the current transfer is not significantly limited by inductance but mainly by the switching speed of the IGBT. This current transfer is faster, and the modeling of this phenomenon is not presented in this work. Figure 4 shows an example of the HyS current in each component calculated with equations (4) (5) (6).

Situation 2 - When HyS with a discrete diode is operating with negative I_{HyS} , a similar effect is observed when MOSFET is turned on after dead time. Part of the current that flows through the discrete diode will

Fig. 4. Calculated currents (equations (4) to (6)) for the HyS switch considering current dynamics when operated with switching pattern 3.

start to flow through the SiC MOSFET. The current transfer will follow a similar dynamic due to parasitic inductance. Current in the MOSFET is described by (7), with time constant τ_2 (8). For simplicity $I'_{HyS} = -I_{HyS}$ and $t'' = t - T_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} I_M(t'') &= \frac{I'_{HyS} \cdot R_D + V_D}{R_{DSON} + R_D} + \\ &+ \frac{(-I'_{HyS} \cdot R_{DSON} - V_I)e^{-\frac{t''}{\tau_2}}}{R_{DSON} + R_D} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\tau_2 = \frac{2L}{R_{DSON} + R_D} \quad (8)$$

III. TEST FOR HYBRID SWITCH LARGE SIGNAL MODEL VALIDATION

To verify the dynamic described in Section II, the current in the MOSFET was captured with an oscilloscope, for different parasitic inductances in the diode. The diode was chosen as the component where the parasitic inductance would be varied since it was the simplest way to do it. Figure 5 shows the test circuit, while Figure 6 shows the test setup. Components in TO-247 packaging were used for the sake of simplicity.

Three conditions are tested for the diode parasitic inductance. The first one is the parasitic inductance of the original device (in TO-247 packaging). To increase the inductance, a hard wire is soldered to the 3 pins of the component in order to double its length. The third case is creating a coil in the center pin, made with the same hard wire, to further increase inductance. The resulting diodes conditions are shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 5. Circuit used to validate the RL dynamic present in the HyS.

Fig. 6. Experimental setup used to validate the RL dynamic present in the HyS.

Fig. 7. Diode setup to change the parasitic inductance.

Current I_{HyS} is controlled by changing the duty cycle of the high side switch, considering the load resistance and bus voltage. In this first test, current was adjusted to 44 A. Fixed dead time of 1 μ s was used to turn on the low side MOSFET. Figure 8 shows the MOSFET current for each tested parasitic inductance. For simplicity currents are shown as positive which means that they flow from source to drain in this test.

Fig. 8. MOSFET current captured in the test for different parasitic inductances during turn-on of SiC MOSFET with current flowing from source to drain.

Current waveforms show that the diode inductance affects the current behavior during dead time. Before turning on the MOSFET, higher currents will flow through the MOSFET body diode if one increases the discrete diode parasitic inductance. Since the discrete diode has lower voltage drop (for a given current) than the MOSFET body diode, higher parasitic inductance results in higher losses. The same di/dt reduction process can be seen after SiC MOSFET is turned off, and the half-bridge returns to a dead time state where both bottom and top devices are off, when the current slowly goes from the MOSFET body diode to the discrete diode.

In order to verify the model for the current dynamics, only the interval when the MOSFET is on will be considered. A curve fitting technique is used in the current waveforms of Figure 8 aiming to calculate R_{DSON} , R_D , V_D and L given in equation (7). Table I shows the values found, and compare these values to the datasheet values of the components.

Values obtained from the curve fitting shown in Table I are close to datasheet values. The difference in the R_{DSON} can be explained by the presence of the current shunt, with a 9.93 $m\Omega$ resistance, in the test setup. As for the diode resistance, a socket was used to connect the diode to the circuit and the contact resistance can be responsible for the verified difference.

TABLE I
CIRCUIT PARAMETERS IDENTIFIED BY CURVE FITTING OF
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS COMPARED TO DATA-SHEET VALUES

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Datasheet
$R_{DS_{ON}}$ (m Ω)		83.3		75
R_D (m Ω)		21.4		15
V_D (mV)		953		935
L (nH)	24	30	42	-

IV. IMPACT OF CURRENT DYNAMICS ON HYBRID SWITCH LOSSES

HyS conduction losses will be impacted by the current dynamics shown in Section III. A first approach to quantify it is to see the HyS voltage drop as the voltage drop of the MOSFET. Thus, instantaneous conduction losses can be calculated by (9) and shown in Figure 9 for the switching pattern 3 from Figure 2.

$$P_{HyS}(t) = I_{HyS} \cdot R_{DS_{ON}} \cdot I_M(t) \quad (9)$$

Fig. 9. Hybrid instantaneous conduction losses considering current dynamics, separated into different regions concerning different dynamic phenomenon.

Figure 9 represents in the graph:

- $P_{HyS}(t)$: Instantaneous hybrid switch power losses (Red line).
- P_{SiC} : Conduction loss when the SiC MOSFET is conducting I_{HyS} current alone.
- $P_{SiC+IGBT}$: Conduction loss when the SiC MOSFET and Si IGBT are sharing I_{HyS} current.
- $E_{C_{HyS}}$: Ideal HyS conduction energy lost in a period, if the current was shared by Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET during the entire period (Grey area).

- $\Delta E_{C_{delay}}$: Extra conduction energy lost due to the switching delay imposed between Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET (Green area).
- $\Delta E_{C_{RL}}$: Extra conduction energy lost due to the exiting current RL dynamics explained in Section II (Blue area).

This graph clearly shows the extra conduction energy in the hybrid switch when a delay is applied between switching signals of Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET. Note that this delay can be optimized to reduce HyS total losses, as there is a trade-off between switching losses and delay, as shown [7].

Since these extra energies are lost at each switching cycle, they can be seen as switching losses, and this can limit the switching frequency of the hybrid switch. These extra losses can be integrated in equation (9) and the mean conduction power loss in the HyS can be calculated as:

$$\overline{P_{HyS}} = \frac{E_{C_{HyS}} + \Delta E_{C_{delay}} + \Delta E_{C_{RL}}}{T_2 - T_1} \quad (10)$$

with each energy calculated by (11), (12) and (13).

$$E_{C_{HyS}} = P_{SiC+IGBT} \cdot (T_2 - T_1) \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta E_{C_{delay}} = (P_{SiC} - P_{SiC+IGBT}) \cdot (T_{d_{on}} + T_{d_{off}}) \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta E_{C_{RL}} = \int_{T_1+T_{d_{on}}}^{T_2-T_{d_{off}}} (P_{HyS}(t) - P_{SiC+IGBT}) dt \quad (13)$$

with the SiC and HyS instantaneous conduction losses given by

$$P_{SiC} = R_{DS_{ON}} \cdot I_{HyS}^2 \quad (14)$$

$$P_{SiC+IGBT} = \frac{R_{DS_{ON}} \cdot (R_I \cdot I_{HyS}^2 + V_I \cdot I_{HyS})}{R_{DS_{ON}} + R_I} \quad (15)$$

The same process of writing instantaneous losses and identifying the energies that are part of conduction losses can be done for the individual devices that compose the HyS. Therefore, extra energy lost in the SiC MOSFET, and the energy that is not lost in the Si IGBT due to the HyS dynamics can be determined. These values are necessary to calculate conduction loss and junction temperature of each device. This analysis can be used to verify thermal limits of the hybrid switch, but is beyond the scope of this paper, and will be explored in future works.

V. HYBRID SWITCH EXTRA CONDUCTION ENERGY MEASUREMENT

To measure extra conduction energy described in Section IV, the current shown in Figure 4 is applied in the hybrid switch. Circuit represented in Figure 10 and the appropriate gate signals for low side devices are used to achieve this. Test current is defined by selecting V_{BUS} and R_{LOAD} . The low side Si IGBT is switched with different periods $T_I = T_2 - T_1$ and off times $T_{dTOTAL} = t_{don} + t_{doff}$. To allow current to reach steady state value in the RL load, this pulse is repeated N times. During these N periods, that correspond to the total test time T_{test} , the low side SiC MOSFET is kept turned on. Figure 11 shows the gate signals of the low side devices.

Fig. 10. Proposed circuit to measure extra conduction energy in the HyS due to the RL dynamics present in the HyS and delay between Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET switching signals.

Total test time T_{test} has to be large enough to allow the RL load to reach steady state current. T_{test} should also be kept as small as possible to avoid self-heating of the devices under test. Measured data are then processed, identifying the instantaneous power losses P_{Hys} and the mean power $\overline{P_{Hys}}$ losses in the HyS during one period T_I . The setup used is shown in Figure 12. Figure 13 shows an example of captured device voltage

Fig. 11. Gate signals for the proposed test method for measuring extra conduction energy in a hybrid switch.

and current waveforms and the calculated instantaneous power losses, that have the waveform similar to that proposed in the models from Sections II and IV.

Fig. 12. Experimental setup to measure extra conduction energy in a HyS.

To measure the extra conduction energy, the test is done for different periods T_I , and thus switching frequencies f for the Si IGBT. This test can be done in two ways. The first is to keep T_{dTOTAL} constant for all tested f . The other option is to recalculate T_{dTOTAL} to keep the duty cycle of the Si IGBT constant. These two approaches allow us to measure different energies lost in the hybrid switch and will be discussed in the following subsections.

A. Test at Constant T_{dTOTAL}

The first possibility is to have T_{dTOTAL} fixed in each tested frequencies. In this case $\overline{P_{Hys}}$ can be rewritten as

Fig. 13. Example of captured voltage and current waveforms and the calculated instantaneous power losses of each device of the HyS.

function of the frequency as (16), with $f = \frac{1}{T_I}$.

$$\overline{P_{HyS}}(f) = (\Delta E_{C_{RL}} + \Delta E_{C_{delay}}) \cdot f + P_{SiC+IGBT} \quad (16)$$

The IGBT was switched at switching frequencies of 10, 20, 40, 50, 80 and 100 kHz. The test was done for constant $T_{d_{TOTAL}}$ of 1, 2, 5 and 10 μ s. Test current was fixed at 63.5 A. Results are shown in two forms where the first is in a graph form in Figure 14.

The graph shows the linear relation between mean conduction loss in the hybrid switch and frequency. To further confirm this linear relation, the linear coefficients that best fit the test result are calculated and compared to (16). Coefficient values are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
EXTRA CONDUCTION ENERGY MEASURED IN THE HYBRID SWITCH.

$T_{d_{TOTAL}}$	$\Delta E_{C_{RL}} + \Delta E_{C_{delay}}$ (mJ)	$P_{SiC+IGBT}$ (W)
1	0.32	120.2
2	0.52	119.8
5	1.07	119.7
10	2.03	118.3

Table shows that the slope increases with the time delay represented by $T_{d_{TOTAL}}$ in this case. This is due

Fig. 14. Mean conduction losses in the hybrid switch with fixed time delay and for different switching frequencies and off time ($T_{d_{TOTAL}}$)

to the increase in the $\Delta E_{C_{delay}}$ that increases with the total delay. This is the expected behavior, analyzing (12) with $T_{d_{TOTAL}} = T_{d_{on}} + T_{d_{off}}$. We also see consistent values for the HyS losses when SiC MOSFET and Si IGBT share the current ($P_{SiC+IGBT}$), that depend only on device characteristics as shown in (15).

B. Fixed duty cycle D

To keep duty cycle D constant, $T_{d_{TOTAL}}$ is recalculated as:

$$D = \frac{T_I - T_{d_{TOTAL}}}{T_I} \quad (17)$$

$$T_{d_{TOTAL}} = T_I(1 - D) = \frac{1 - D}{f}. \quad (18)$$

In this case $\overline{P_{HyS}}$ is given by (19).

$$\overline{P_{HyS}}(f) = \Delta E_{C_{RL}} \cdot f + D \cdot P_{SiC+IGBT} + (1 - D) \cdot P_{SiC} \quad (19)$$

This scenario was done with fixed D of 0.3, 0.5 and 0.7. The graph for $\overline{P_{HyS}}$ as a function of IGBT switching frequency and for different D is shown in Figure 15.

When D is kept constant, the increasing conduction losses with switching frequency are still verified, reinforcing that RL dynamics and delay between Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET has a strong influence in switching losses. The slope of three curves in Figure 15 corresponds to $\Delta E_{C_{RL}}$ in (19). Coefficients of linear fitting these curve are presented in Table III.

From the constant duty cycle test, measured $\Delta E_{C_{RL}}$ was consistent between the different D as expect. For the

Fig. 15. Mean conduction power losses in the hybrid switch with fixed IGBT duty cycle.

TABLE III

MEASURED EXTRA CONDUCTION ENERGY DUE TO CURRENT DYNAMICS IN THE HYBRID SWITCH.

Duty Cycle	$\Delta E_{C_{RL}}$ (mJ)	$D \cdot P_{SiC+IGBT} + (1 - D) \cdot P_{SiC}$ (W)
0.3	0.20	244.7
0.5	0.21	207.7
0.7	0.19	171.8

tested components used in this specific setup, $\Delta E_{C_{RL}} = 0.2$ mJ. This value is not irrelevant when compared to the total energy including delay time, therefore this dynamic is not irrelevant and increase losses in the hybrid switch. This energy is lost when switching due to the RL dynamics of the current in the HyS. To reduce these losses the path between IGBT and SiC MOSFET has to be as small as possible to reduce its parasitic inductance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work focused on the dynamic behavior of Si IGBT and SiC MOSFET in a hybrid switch (HyS). Current dynamics imposed by parasitic inductance when the HyS is operated with switching patterns used to reduce switching losses is presented and analytically modeled. A test methodology to measure conduction losses in the hybrid switch, and separate the static losses and dynamics conduction losses, is proposed and test results are presented. These results show the occurrence of losses that do not depend on the delay applied between IGBT and SiC, and that depend on the parasitic inductance between these devices, which validates the

analysis presented here. The proposed test setup provides more accurate information about HyS losses, that can be used in future works to optimize total component losses and achieve better thermal balance between devices composing the hybrid switch.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Kayser, F. Pfirsch, F.-J. Niedernostheide, R. Baburske, and H.-G. Eckel, Novel Si-SiC hybrid switch and its design optimization path, in 2022 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices and ICs (ISPSD), May 2022, pp. 225228. doi: 10.1109/ISPSD49238.2022.9813676.
- [2] X. Song, A. Q. Huang, M.-C. Lee, and C. Peng, High voltage Si/SiC hybrid switch: An ideal next step for SiC, in 2015 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices & ICs (ISPSD), Hong Kong, China, May 2015, pp. 289292. doi: 10.1109/ISPSD.2015.7123446.
- [3] X. Song and A. Q. Huang, 6.5kV FREEDM-Pair: Ideal high power switch capitalizing on Si and SiC, in 2015 17th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE15 ECCE-Europe), Geneva, Sep. 2015, pp. 19. doi: 10.1109/EPE.2015.7309243.
- [4] Z. Li et al., Optimal control strategies for SiC MOSFET and Si IGBT based hybrid switch, in 2018 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC), San Antonio, TX, USA, Mar. 2018, pp. 17171721. doi: 10.1109/APEC.2018.8341249.
- [5] Y. Fu and H. Ren, A Novel Single-Gate Driver Circuit for SiC+Si Hybrid Switch With Variable Triggering Pattern, IEEE Trans. Power Electron., vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 1195311966, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2021.3069824.
- [6] Z. Li et al., Dynamic Gate Delay Time Control of Si/SiC Hybrid Switch for Loss Minimization in Voltage Source Inverter, IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Topics Power Electron., vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 41604170, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2021.3137332.
- [7] H. Qin, R. Wang, Q. Xun, W. Chen, and S. Xie, Switching Time Delay Optimization for SiC+Si Hybrid Device in a Phase-Leg Configuration, IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 3754237556, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3055244.
- [8] H. Liu, T. Zhao, X. Xu, and J. Zhou, Conduction Time Variation-Based Active Thermal Control Method for Si and SiC Hybrid Switch, in 2022 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE), Oct. 2022, pp. 15. doi: 10.1109/ECCE50734.2022.9947678.
- [9] Z. He, Z. Li, F. Yuan, C. Zeng, X. Jiang, and J. Wang, Active Thermal Control of SiC/Si Hybrid Switch, in 2018 IEEE International Power Electronics and Application Conference and Exposition (PEAC), Nov. 2018, pp. 14. doi: 10.1109/PEAC.2018.8590287.

- [10] B. Cougo, L. M. F. Morais, G. Segond, R. Riva, and H. Tran Duc, Influence of PWM Methods on Semiconductor Losses and Thermal Cycling of 15-kVA Three-Phase SiC Inverter for Aircraft Applications, *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 4, Art. no. 4, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.3390/electronics9040620.